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A MATHEMATICAL MODEL FOR ACCESS CONTROL THROUGH TRUST MANAGEMENT IN UBIQUITOUS COMPUTING**D. S. SHELAR*, P. G. ANDHARE, S. B. GAIKWAD AND P. A. THAKRE****ABSTRACT**

In the ubiquitous computing environment of wireless access control, access is granted on having successful interactions with other devices/nodes/agents. Consequently, the wireless technologies further extend the association between devices to interact with each other with respect to provide access control. For mobile nodes, many times associations are volatile in nature. There is always a risk associated with such interactions when there is no trust amongst them. From a security perspective, there is a requirement for a proper mechanism to build trust so that nodes can interact with each other for the safe sharing of information. Many researchers have proposed trust models in which the credibility, mobility, and reliability of requester agents are not considered. In this study, we proposed the trust calculation model in ubiquitous computing by considering parameters like credibility, transitivity, reliability, and mobility. This trust calculation model can be incorporated in Ubiquitous Computing for better decision making for access control.

Keywords and phrase: Access Control; Ubiquitous Computing; Trust; Credibility; Mobility; Reliability; Transitivity.

1. INTRODUCTION

In day to day life, the role of computer technology is to integrate the public and private sectors fields such as trade, logistics, industry, transport, and healthcare through electronic devices. To address this issue, Mark Weiser [1] first time introduced the paradigm shift from one to one computer to one to many computers through ubiquitous computing (UbiComp) in which electronic nodes are fully connected and make them available for sharing and processing the data because UbiComp has capacity to remove the complexities of computing so that the various activities can be done efficiently with optimal use of memory.

Ubiquitous computing is the paradigm which postulates a world where people are surrounded by computing devices and a computing infrastructure that supports each other in everything that people perform in the physical world.

The focus is on developing ubiquitous computer systems to support people in their daily activities of various tasks of the physical world even though the electronic nodes are mobile. UbiComp provides access to all electronic user nodes on the basis of smart interactions. The smart interaction refers to the interaction made with the credible nodes which provide trustworthy information. If a user is trustworthy, the experience will be pleasant even if the product is not perfect in a business transaction. If node A trusts node B and then they will remain loyal to each other because loyal nodes are incredibly useful in the strategy of access control to grant access to other electronics nodes. This Means, when we are able to interact in such a way that builds trust, we naturally build personal credibility.

The emergence of these devices has created many security issues for which solutions and existing mechanisms are sufficient, especially concerning the problems of authentication and user's private data protection. So, one of the important threats of ubiquitous computing is to maintain privacy which may cause its popularity to decrease. Many researchers contributed a lot to data security in access control for UbiComp. Hua Wang [2] and his team presented an access control model to protect services and devices in the UbiComp environment, which allows the access restrictions directly on services and object documents. This model provides a mechanism to build relationships between models and objects. Finally, comparisons with related works are analyzed. Several studies are also available on the security requirements for ubiquitous computing ([3]–[6]).

In this study, we have proposed a mathematical model for the calculation of trust of an agent in access control for UbiComp by considering the factors like credibility, reliability, transitivity, and mobility of an agent and tried to present the best solution for access control.

The remaining section of the paper is organized as follows: Section 2 explains the motivation for our model. Section 3 explains the literature review of the various approaches regarding trust models in UbiComp. The proposed mathematical model is presented in Section 4 followed by Section 5 and 6 which explain results and conclusion respectively.

2. MOTIVATION

In electronic social media (ESM) anyone can freely share information on the basis of relationships through communication and even develop a new relationship with others who are strangers. But a relationship with strangers may cause to disclose privacy. So, it is necessary to check the trustworthiness of the people in the process of information sharing. Therefore there should be an access control policy regulated by the owner.

Many traditional access control mechanisms are available for ESM ([19]-[21]). But it has its own limitations because the owner-user relationship is dynamic. After a certain period of time users may disclose the owner's private information. So it becomes necessary to monitor the behavior of user continuously and check their trustworthiness of users. In order to address this issue, Baek and Kim [22] proposed a dynamic trust-based access control for the online social network in which they evaluated the dynamic trust values so that owners can monitor negative behavior and decide whether the access should be granted to a user or not.

Since the level of access control from device A to device B is directly proportional to the trust device A is holding for device B [7]. Access control and trust are closely related as the level of access granted by a particular device to another device or service depend on the level of trust between these devices.

Over the time trust has been an established concept in network security and therefore it is treated as an emerging field of ubiquitous computing with respect to access control. Many existing studies identified that the trust as an alternative to collaborate in a world without passwords and necessary certificates. It seems to be the logical choice that we are simply to integrate its workings and mechanisms into our new security concepts for ubiquitous computing.

Even though trust-based access control is gaining momentum in the field of ubiquitous computing by allowing electronic agents to compute the 'trustworthiness' of other electronic agents based on their interactions, much remains unclear when it comes to defining the problem we are trying to solve. So, it is obvious to raise the question, what is the role of trust in access control for Ubicomp? This type of question can be addressed by giving access to the agent by the positive interactions happening with even third party users.

In most of the work related to ubicomp, trust has focused on expanding the trust concepts from network security, i.e. granting or denying access not simply based on pre-computed certificates, but rather depending on a particular context. By taking inspiration from the earlier contribution regarding the role of trust for denial or granting the access in Ubicomp. We have been motivated to present the model for trust calculation by considering parameters like credibility, reliability, transitivity, and mobility.

3. RELATED LITERATURE

In ubiquitous computing, the trust amongst the agents is one of the important factor for rendering access to other agents. It also helps to deal with security issues. Many researchers have presented their views through their work. Matt Blaze et al. [9] first proposed decentralized trust-management Policymaker where they have presented the comprehensive approach to the trust management, based on a simple language for specifying trusted actions and trust relationships that will facilitate the development of security features in a wide range of network services.

Jameel et al.[10] described the trust model which is based on the vectors of trust values of different entities in ubiquitous computing by capturing uncertainties occurred in his model. The trust value is calculated by considering various factors such as peer reputation, confidence, history of past interaction, and time-based trust evaluation factor. Also efficiently handled the false recommendations of entities.

Colin English [11] and his team has intended to assume that the trust and cryptographic security are considered to be orthogonal to each other by assuming the existence of reliable encryption techniques and focus on the characteristics of a model that supports the management of the trust relationships between two devices during ad-hoc interactions.

R He et al. [12] developed a trust management framework for a multi-cloud environment to effectively evaluate the trustworthiness of Cloud Service Providers and Trust Service Providers based trust management architecture using subjective and objective trust.

Prajapati et al. [14] introduced a trust management model to manage the trust and its properties for software as a service in a cloud computing environment. The Trust model is constructed based on several trust properties such as asymmetry, reflexivity, context dependency, scalability, partial transitivity and Uncertainty. Malika Yaici et al.[15] proposed context aware authentication system using trust management between client and servers even among servers. Also presented is an algorithm to calculate context based trust.

Mahalle et al. [7] also presented a Fuzzy approach to the Trust Based Access Control model where the trust is calculated using uncertain parameters such as experience knowledge, recommendation. Nalini Mhetre and her co-workers [8] presented an experience model for Ubicomp. In which they proposed a mathematical model for experience of nodes with other nodes by considering the parameters such as history, reliability, and transitivity and ubiquity so as to grant access control. In this study, we have proposed a mathematical approach for access control in Ubicomp using the trustworthiness of agents. But while calculating trustworthiness in [[7]-[8]] the factors like credibility and mobility of an electronic agents are not taken into consideration, so we proposed a trust calculation model by considering those factors.

4. CHALLENGES

Many researchers presented an access control models using trust in ubiquitous computing but those models are not fully acceptable due to privacy issues of owners and prevention of malicious users. One of the reasons for creating this issue is to have inappropriate trust value of user-node by considering limited attributes such as recommendations (by the third party), history, transitivity, and reliability and also the calculation of each attribute. In proposed the model we have considered credibility and mobility of user-node so that on the basis of previous interactions we can calculate up to how much degree is the user-node node credible?

5. PROPOSED MODEL

Existing fuzzy trust based access control (FTBACM) model calculate trustworthiness of each device or group of devices based on three components such as knowledge, experience and recommendation but the proposed trustworthiness model presented in this article with attributes like Credibility (C_r), Reliability (R_l), Transitivity (T_r) and Mobility (M_b) of requester agent where C_r , R_l and T_r are the real numbers belongs to $[0,1]$.

5.1 Credibility

Recently electronic social media has become an integrated part of everyday life. However, the owners are facing challenges of being susceptible to wrong information and rumors. Therefore the credibility of user nodes in social media needs to be checked. Castillo et al. [24] presented in his seminal paper on information credibility of news propagated through Twitter using user's profile information, network information, and user's behavior (tweets and retweets) to assess the credibility of tweets.

Barbier and Liu [23] proposed a method to find provenance paths leading to sources of the information to evaluate its credibility. A research article by Jiayi Sun [25], evaluated the credibility of social media information based on user perception by considering three parameters such as subject credibility, source credibility and content credibility of electronic social media. Looking toward the significance of the credibility of user nodes, we considered this attribute in order to increase the effectiveness of trust value.

Credibility component of any device can be calculated on the basis of past interaction that happened with other devices. Rating of the past interaction is done to be 0 to 1. If the interaction factor is close to 1 then it is said to be successful and if it is close to zero then it is said to be unsuccessful. Let I_j be the past interaction happened where $I_j \in [0,1]$, $j = 1, 2, \dots, n$.

Credibility (C_r) = $\left[\left(\sum_{j=1}^{j=n} I_j \right) / n \right]$ and the values of $C_r \in [0,1]$.

If $C_r \geq 0.8$ then the agent is treated as credible (to be decided by owner-agent) .

5.2 Transitivity

In trust management, an agent A is not directly interacted with an agent C but authentication is required between them where the trust transfer plays an important role through intermediate agent B. Trust transfer happens if an agent B recommend agent A that an agent C is trustworthy if an agent A is trustor and agent B is trustee. But the magnitude of trust between agents B and C and A and C may differ.

Nowadays, the trustworthiness among the agents that do not know each other. In access control this is a big challenge. This issue may be addressed through trust transitivity. Many researchers addressed this issue, Josang and Pope [16] used belief theory for deriving transitive trust using the belief operators of subjective logic described trust transitivity in online interaction among strangers. Xiang Qiu et al.[17] described a trust transitivity model based on evidence theory by capturing uncertainty occurring in the model.

Xu and Fung [18] proposed a risk-defined trust transitivity model for group decision making in social networks with the help of a risk-defined trust propagation operator that can propagate trust and distrust information based on risk bearing level defining factors like trust, distrust, uncertainty and inconsistency.

Since the magnitude of trust between agents A, B and B, C is not the same. So in order to minimize the risk, we considered the trust between A and C is the magnitude of the minimum of trust between A, B and B, C.

Let α, β, γ be the trust between (A, B), (B, C) and (A, C).

$$\gamma = \min (\alpha, \beta)$$

where $\alpha, \beta, \gamma \in [0,1]$

5.3 Reliability

Trust is incomplete without accurate reliability. In the UbiComp environment the access control, the reliability of an agent to which the access is granted is highly needed to be known. The reliability of an agent can be calculated on the basis of the degree to which the agent shows consistently good performance in interactions. Node A is reliable to node B only if A consistently keeps good interactions with B.

Consistently good interactions in a short period of time or with less number of good consistent interactions may invite less reliability. This degeneracy can be overcome by finding the coefficient of correlation between two sets of interaction values.

Reliability of an agent is one of the important parameter in wireless sensor network (WSN). Access is granted when an agent is highly reliable. There is a set of interactions that happened between two agents in two time periods in months or years. If two sets of interactions are correlated up to the desired level then the agent is reliable.

Let $(I_j)_{t_1}$ and $(I_j)_{t_2}$ be the interaction values between two agents in time slot t_1 and t_2 respectively. The correlation coefficient between $(I_j)_{t_1}$ and $(I_j)_{t_2}$ is

$$r_l = \frac{\sum_{j=1}^{j=n} \{[(I_j)_{t_1} - \bar{(I_j)_{t_1}}][(I_j)_{t_2} - \bar{(I_j)_{t_2}}]\}}{\sqrt{\sum_{j=1}^{j=n} [(I_j)_{t_1} - \bar{(I_j)_{t_1}}]^2 \sum_{j=1}^{j=n} [(I_j)_{t_2} - \bar{(I_j)_{t_2}}]^2}} \quad (1)$$

where

1. $\bar{(I_j)_{t_1}}$ and $\bar{(I_j)_{t_2}}$ be the mean values of $(I_j)_{t_1}$ and $(I_j)_{t_2}$.
2. $-1 \leq r \leq 1$.

For convenience the reliability factor we considered $R_i = |r_l|$.

5.4 Mobility

Mobility is one of the important aspects when a large number of agents play in UbiComp. In online social networks also users provide access to unknown requester-agents even if it is mobile (not stationary) to build relationships. If requester-agents move far away from user-agent, in this case the proper interaction may not happen which may result in the risk of disseminating unclear information. In order to address this issue traditional role based access control models are applied in online social networking. But those models are not suitable for the non-stationary environment because user behaviour is unpredictable in terms of distance. So, we used the mobility factor range of requester-agents which is one of the important contributors for trust calculations. The remarkable permission to the agent is granted when the distance of the requester-node from the user-node is within the specified range.

Let r and o be the positions of requester-agent and user-agent respectively.

Let s be the distance between r and o that is $d(r, o) = s$

and $R_{(r,o)}$ be the region covered by user-agent.

$$R_{(r,o)} = \{x/d(r_i, o_i) \leq s\}$$

If a requester-agent lies in the region $R_{(r,o)}$ then the interaction may happen whether it is successful or nor it is immaterial. In this case we assign the value of mobility factor is 1 else 0.

5.5 Trust (T) Calculation

Step1: If the mobility factor of the requester agent is 1 then calculate trust of a requester-agent using the following formula.

$$T = w_1 C_r + w_2 T_r + w_3 R_l \quad (2)$$

where $T, w_1, w_2, w_3 \in [0,1]$ such that $\sum_{k=1}^{k=3} w_k = 1$

Also w_1, w_2 and w_3 are the weights assigned to credibility, transitivity and reliability respectively. If the T is close to 1, the agent/requester node is said to be trustworthy.

Step:2If the mobility factor of the requester agent is 0 then ignore the requester-agent that is access should be denied.

Figure 1: Flow Chart

5.6 Experimental Results

An experiment on 15 user/requester nodes is performed as per the significance of the attributes in 8 scenarios. We came to the conclusion that the trust value of an agent is as appropriate for the 60% weightage of reliability, 30% weightage of credibility and 10% weightage of transitivity. It means that the reliability factor is more important in trust calculation. Figure 2 to Figure 9 shows the result of the trust calculation in this scenario. However, the above weightage may vary from problem to problem and situation to situation.

Figures : 2-9

6. CONCLUSION

In ubiquitous computing, simultaneous interactions within many to many nodes happen. In such an environment, malicious nodes may provide insufficient or incorrect information that may cause issues of privacy and security. In order to address this issue, we presented a mathematical model for access control through trust management in ubiquitous computing using parameters such as credibility, transitivity, reliability and mobility, which is the best suited to provide access to the requester-agent/node. Also shown that the presented trust calculation leads to better decision making with respect to weightage of three attributes like credibility, transitivity and reliability.

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